

Studies on Synthesis of Halogenated Phenothiazine Derivatives

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Manuscript received 12 October 1987, revised 4 February 1988, accepted 21 March 1988

1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-(substituted-benzthiazol-2'-ylaminoacetyl)phenothiazines have been synthesised by condensation of the chloroacetyl derivative of phenothiazine with substituted-2-aminobenzthiazoles. The halogenated derivatives of phenothiazine were screened for their antibacterial efficacy.

PHENOTHIAZINE derivatives are found to possess various biological activities¹. Benzthiazole and its many derivatives are particularly important as far as their relation to the industrial applications are concerned. It has also various types of biological activities. 2-Aminobenzthiazole has fungicidal activity and is also active against bacteria². 2-Phenyl-substituted-benzthiazole halogen derivatives are active against dermatophytes protozoa and gram +ve bacteria³.

With a view to prepare better therapeutic agents, compounds containing both the heterocyclic moieties, i.e. chlorophenothiazine and 2-amino-substituted-benzthiazoles, were synthesised according to Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Backmann IR 20 spectrophotometer. Structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, m.m.p. and ir spectra.

The ir spectra of the compounds show characteristic bands at 1 500 (C-N), 1 750 (C=O), 1 450 (CH₂CO), 680 and 1 215 (C-S and C-N stretch of phenothiazine heterocycle) and 820 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) which supported the validity of the compounds.

1,3,7,9-Tetrachlorophenothiazine: To diphenylamine (0.4 mol) and thionyl chloride (260 ml) was added dropwise. The resulting mixture was heated under reflux till the evolution of SO₂ and HCl gases were complete. The contents were then cooled and poured carefully on crushed ice. The resulting solid product was isolated and recrystallised from benzene, (70%, 94.3 g), m.p. 236° (lit. 235°) (Found: N, 4.00; S, 9.30. C₁₂H₈Cl₄NS requires: N, 4.15; S, 9.49%).

1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-chloroacetylphenothiazine: 1,3,7,9-Tetrachlorophenothiazine (0.1 mol) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.15 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) were refluxed in a water-bath for 2.5 h. P₂O₅ (0.5 g) was added as condensing agent. On evaporation of the solvent the resulting solid product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene, (66%, 27.29 g), m.p. 180° (Found: N, 3.20; S, 7.59. C₁₄H₆Cl₄NOS requires: N, 3.38; S, 7.73%).

2-Aminobenzthiazole: Aniline (0.1 mol) and KCNS (0.4 mol) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (150 ml). Bromine (0.1 mol in 75 ml glacial acetic acid) was then added to it dropwise maintaining the temperature around 30°. After complete addition, stirring was continued for 8-10 h and filtered. The filtrate on neutralisation with aqueous

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF PHENOTHIAZINE DERIVATIVES*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Interpretation zone of inhibition** (µg/disk)	
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	165	+	-
2.	4-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	160	++	+
3.	5-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	185	+	-
4.	6-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	142	+	-
5.	4,6-(Cl) ₂	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	168	+	-
6.	6-Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrCl ₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	200	+	+
7.	4-NO ₂	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	151	++	+
8.	5-NO ₂	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	135	+	-
9.	6-NO ₂	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	190	-	-
10.	5-OCH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	140	-	-
11.	6-OCH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	162	++	-
12.	6-OO ₂ H	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	145	+	+
13.	5-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	170	+	+
14.	6-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	175	-	-
15.	5-CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	140	-	+
16.	6-CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	132	-	+
17.	5,6-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	135	+	+
18.	6-COO ₂ H	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	150	-	-
19.	6-COOH	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	139	-	-
20.	6-NHCOOH	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₁ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	180	+	+

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, S analyses.

**Growth inhibition zone diameter: (+) = ≤ 20 mm, (++) = > 20 mm.

NH₃ gave the solid product which was filtered, washed and recrystallised from rectified spirit, (60%, 9.0 g), m.p. 132° (Found: N, 18.48; S, 21.10. C₇H₈N₂S requires: N, 18.66; S, 21.33%).

1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-(benzthiazol-2'-ylaminoacetyl)phenothiazine: 1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-chloroacetylphenothiazine (0.005 mol) and 2-amino-benzthiazole (0.005 mol) were refluxed in benzene for 3–4 h. The contents were then cooled and the solvent was removed by distillation. The resulting solid product was washed, dried and recrystallised from benzene.

Similarly, other compounds were prepared. The physical and pharmacological data are recorded in Table 1.

Pharmacological screening: 1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-(substituted-benzthiazol-2'-ylaminoacetyl)phenothiazines were screened for antibacterial activity, against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by cup-plate⁴ method. The testing was carried out in 1:4 dioxane solution at a concentration of 10 µg ml⁻¹. The zone of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) are recorded in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University for facilities and Junior Research Fellowships to two of them (K.N.B. and A.M.D.) and also thankful to Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh, for pharmacological screening.

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